

INVESTIGATING AND RANKING OF THE EFFECTIVE FACTORS AND OBSTACLES TO THE IMPLEMENTATION OF ENTERPRISE RESOURCE PLANNING (ERP) IN IRAN

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Abstract

Purpose: Generally, comprehensive enterprise resource planning (ERP) systems are used to automate business processes, enable users to share data simultaneously and produce real-time data within an organization. Based on the Mackenzie 7s model, the present study was conducted to examine and rank the factors and obstacles affecting enterprise resource planning (ERP) implementation in Iran, which added two additional aspects affecting organization resource planning as Check 9 variables: The common values, organizational structure, strategy, organizational systems, management and leadership styles, employees, manpower skills, monitoring and feedback, and vendor support. **Design/methodology/approach:** The nine variables were formulated as nine hypotheses. Both the survey and the research employed quantitative methods. In this study, the statistical population consisted of managers of ERP manufacturing companies and consultants in this field in Iran, and 60 managers were surveyed. **Finding:** According to the results of this study, all nine factors studied had a significant impact on the implementation of ERP in companies in Iran. As a result, there is a significant difference between the current situation and the desired situation, and the desired situation is on average higher than the current situation. Further, the findings indicated that there was a significant difference between the nine factors in the implementation of ERP in Iranian organizations. **Originality/ value:** Employees, oversight and feedback, management and leadership style, and in the optimal position, the order of importance is respectively employees, manpower skills, organizational structure, shared values, monitoring and feedback, management and leadership style, strategy, vendor support, and organizational systems.

Keywords: Shared Values, Strategy, Structure, Systems, Leadership Style, Employees, Skills, Vendor Support, Supervision and Feedback, and Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP).

1. Introduction

The recent developments in the business environment of businesses under different headings, such as deregulation, privatization, and globalization; By fostering existing competition, it has allowed large corporations to become multinational companies, thereby inspiring them to seek newer solutions to perpetuate themselves (Arabmazar & Baghoumian, 2006). Meanwhile, ERP-Enterprise Resource Planning system has provided the organization with flexible management, enhancing productivity in addition to giving the company a competitive edge (Mahraz et al., 2019). An ERP system refers to a set of integrated computing applications that includes applications for accounting, inventory control, logistics, and more. As a comprehensive ERP system, the primary goal is to automate business processes, enable the simultaneous use of data by multiple data users, and produce real-time data at the

organizational level (Arabmazar & Baghoumian, 2006). This system includes a set of economic processes that give companies a complete perspective of the future. In addition, as Ram and Corkindale (2014) have noted, an IRP enables task coordination, changes in economic sectors, information movement, and integration (finance, operations, sales, marketing, etc.). Effective implementation of ARP can result in several benefits, including better analysis of facts, the ability to make high quality decisions, improved customer satisfaction, etc. (Shehu and Masunda, 2018).

In recent years, due to the specialization of activities and tasks performed by different units within an organization, the need and significance for comprehensive software to plan, analyze information, and extract integrated and timely reports about all system components have become evident. At the top of the organizational program are integrated organizational systems. Organizations can use these systems to manage their supply chain, receipt, inventory management, customer order management, production planning, transportation, accounting, human resource management, and other business functions (Summers & Nelson, 2004). A resource planning system is one of the most critical factors affecting an organization's successful management of information. Unfortunately, many IRPs have not been successful. The managers of these organizations believe that buying an IRP system is sufficient.

Organizational resource planning systems are very complex information systems, and many factors affect their successful deployment. Organizations should be aware of the most important factors influencing the successful establishment of IRP and provide them (Alam Tabriz et al., 2010). In fact, despite the large investment of resources and time, many companies have not implemented IRP. According to the Gartner Group (2009) report, the IP software market is growing. Researchers have identified many organizations that have faced major challenges in implementing IRP. These studies show that the failure rate may be more than 50% and 20% of organizational efforts have failed. In a study conducted by (Zhang et al. 2003), the success rate of Chinese companies is estimated at 10% (Shukri et al., 2011).

Nevertheless, the ERP system is very efficient for survival in a competitive global environment. In highly competitive markets, organizations need to be customer-focused and profitable, so to achieve success, they need mutual integration across different parts of an organization (Desalgen and Peterson, 2018). Due to the importance of an integrated organizational system for the success, survival, and growth of organizations, in this study, the identification and review of success and failure factors of implementing the organization resource planning project in Iranian companies will be considered with the aim of being able to think of appropriate solutions to solve existing problems after recognizing the obstacles.

2. Problem statement and research principles

In the late twentieth century, the business system was transformed by three critical phenomena: change, the customer, and competition. Due to the increase in awareness and variety of products and services, customers' tastes changed, and they demanded high-quality products and reasonable prices. Advances in technology have increased production capacity and reduced production costs. This posed a difficult competition for suppliers. Therefore, the precondition for survival in today's complex world depends on being closer to customers and

providing value-added services or goods in the shortest possible time. This issue requires integrating the organization's business processes, and one of its solutions is the organizational resource planning system (Rahmani Manesh et al., 2017). Using this system requires organizations looking for fast and efficient business operations (desalegn & pettersson, 2018). In other words, with the increasing acceleration of changes and transformations in the age of communication and information and the instability and unpredictability of change, what helps countries increase productivity and progress is to take advantage of opportunities to compete with other countries by improving creativity and innovation in organizations turns.

In addition to being a management software application, integrated organizational planning also forms the organizational structure based on integrated information systems by bringing together all of the data. There are various definitions of organizational resource planning. As an example, Jack Webb Sublandley describes organizational resource planning as both a solution and a system. Ackermans et al. Organizational resource planning can be defined in a variety of ways, such as from a task, technical, or business perspective, which encompasses the whole organization. Tarantlis et al. believed that organizational resource planning is a system that integrates traditional accounting, production, sales, management and other products, management to provide an "all-in-one" solution that deals with all aspects of the organization's business management. As previous researchers have noted; ERP is not just software, but a kind of business method and by saving organizational processes leads to saving money and time (Rahmani Manesh et al., 2017). However, implementing an ARP system is not an easy task to achieve. And it not only involves a lot of money, effort and time; It includes a set of changes in some business processes as well as significant changes among employees and work practices (Mahraz et al., 2019). A survey of 50 European companies shows that 93% of companies that have implemented IRPs are not very happy with the results. Muscatloo et al. State that 40% of all implementation projects achieve only part of the implementation, and nearly 20% of the projects fail completely. The success rate of IRP implementation projects is less than 30% and according to Gartner Group research, 70% of all IRP projects cannot be fully implemented (Rasoulia, 2015). Given the high number of failures in the implementation of these systems in the world, it is necessary to identify the key factors of success in its implementation. On the other hand, due to the high costs of installing this system and the long time required to implement the system, it is necessary to prepare the necessary prerequisites and arrangements for its acceptance and installation before installation, so that this system can be successfully operated (Angai Et al., 2008; Dezdar and Suleiman, 2009).

The Iranian economy has always been at the forefront of the application of new technologies. The issue of recognizing the success factors of IRP projects in Iranian companies has become a topic of considerable attention in recent years due to the implementation of successful and unsuccessful examples. Considering the importance of the issue to our society, the main question of this research is what factors have been influential in the implementation of the organizational resource planning system (IRP) in Iran? And what was the ranking of those factors examined?

Globalization has led to significant market changes as a result of more competition due to rapid growth. Organizational resource planning has long been considered critical to achieving competitive advantage; however, implementing an IRP system is a complex and expensive process. Understanding the key success factors during the implementation of ARP is therefore crucial in order to ensure its success (Desalgen and Peterson, 2018). In contrast, traditional information systems, despite providing services such as transaction processing, reporting, and providing managers with the necessary information, appear to be inefficient in new business environments (Arab Mazar and Baghomian, 2006). Consequently, it becomes doubly essential to examine and rank the factors and obstacles affecting the implementation of the organization's resource planning system. Today, researchers and IT experts suggest to organizations that the purchase and strategic use of an enterprise resource planning system is an important solution for achieving sustainability in the digital economy. This system has always been considered as an integrated system for increasing the effectiveness and efficiency of organizations. Because all resources of the organization can be managed by managers from different levels of the organization with this system, and with high accuracy, speed, and quality, and this will facilitate the planning process and operations of the organization. So, in order to provide higher quality services and products tailored to the specific needs of each customer, organizations require the presence of such software in order to compete. In general, the present study is important and necessary in the following aspects: Implementation of the IRP system by increasing access to and control of management information and simplification; Increase the opportunity to manage accounting information, and this will greatly affect the reliability of accounting information. Research has also been done in this field. After implementing the system, companies simultaneously experience a decrease in reporting delays and an increase in the level of their optional accruals (Hajijah and Rondeh, 2014).

However, it can be seen today that information and communication technology has affected and transformed not only the information system, but also the way in which organizations operate. Thus, it seems that this technology is able to provide companies with the conditions necessary to react more effectively to environmental changes (Arab Mazar Yazdi and Baghumian, 2006). ARP is an example of these technologies, of which different types (such as SAP, BAN, Jade Edwards, and Oracle) are available to users. The use of these systems is so widespread that their market value is expected to increase from \$ 13.4 billion in 2003 to \$ 15.8 billion in 2008 (Arab Mazar Yazdi and Hanifehzadeh, 2006). Using information technology, organizations are able to perform various tasks such as design, production, sales, after-sales service, accounting, etc. Simultaneously and in different parts of the world, and can at any time provide the necessary information. Receive separately. A mechanism of this kind would seem to require the use of integrated systems that could control all areas of the organization such as finance, warehouse, office, etc. Due to the sensitivity of the industry and the intense competition, Iranian companies also need to change their position from the traditional approach to the system management approach. In Dari et al.'s 2006 study, this vacuum was also identified. Based on a review of 238 articles published between 2000 and 2005, Dari et al. concluded that only 2% of the studies in the field were pre-implementation or compliance studies. Furthermore, implementation articles accounted for 38 percent, while

application and maintenance articles accounted for 25%. In this paper, an attempt is made to provide organizations with a practical tool based on strategic alignment, which has been identified as one of the key factors affecting organizations' readiness to achieve successful implementation of ERP in recent decades. To prepare organizations to the greatest extent possible for the risks associated with implementing these systems (Zarevarosani et al., 2016).

2.1. Hypotheses

- The factor of shared values has a significant impact on the implementation of ERP in companies.
- The factor of strategies has a significant impact on the implementation of ERP in companies.
- The organizational structure factor has a significant impact on the implementation of ERP in companies.
- The factor of organizational systems has a significant impact on the implementation of ERP in companies.
- The factor of management and leadership style has a significant impact on the implementation of ERP in companies.
- The employee factor has a significant impact on the implementation of ERP in companies.
- Manpower skills factor has a significant impact on the implementation of ERP in companies.
- The seller support factor has a significant impact on the implementation of ERP in companies.
- Monitoring and feedback factor has a significant impact on the implementation of ERP in companies.

3. Research methodology

The present study is both an applied research, in terms of its purpose, and a field research, in terms of location, since it collects data about society or a statistical sample, by attending and using a questionnaire. According to the method, this is a descriptive-survey study. The statistical population of the present study is managers of manufacturing companies and consultants who implement ERP systems. Various methods were employed to identify Iranian software companies that produce ERP. This company is estimated to be included in the study. The census or the total number of the sample in this study indicates that the population is equal to the statistical sample in this study. In other words, the sample size is 82 managers of RP manufacturing companies. According to the findings of Nayr et al. (2005), who suggested an acceptable return rate of 56%, the return rate of the questionnaire in this study is within acceptable levels. The present study should be noted that considering that the statistical population consists of project managers, IT managers, and suppliers and consulting companies of ERP systems, it is not possible to consider a specific class or cluster for the community. The researcher had access to the contact information of all members of the

statistical community, made contact with them (in person, by phone, or by email) and requested their cooperation in the study. Due to the fact that the researcher has visited the available sample in order to fill out the questionnaires, the sampling method assumes a non-random and judgmental nature. Moreover, the list available to researchers may not include all members of the research community.

We have collected the required information through a questionnaire in the present study. The content validity index, or CVI, was used to evaluate the validity of the research tool. Upon assessment of the questionnaire's validity, it was found that the initial set of 79 questions was reduced to 66 questions. Due to having less than 79%, questions 7 and 8 related to the project hero, questions 10 and 12 related to specialization, questions 13, 14 and 15 related to focus, and question 58 related to training have been removed. Consequently, by eliminating these questions, the dimensions of the project hero, specialization, and focus could not be measured. In the meantime, question 27 relating to the perspective and the plan has been deleted. As the two questions 28 and 29 are less than 79% in the objectives section, question 30 has been replaced by question 27 in regard to the perspective and the plan. Size, schedule and goals changed.

Cronbach's alpha was used in this study as an indicator of reliability. The number obtained from this test is acceptable when it varies between 0.7 and 1, and being greater than 0.7 indicates the questionnaire is very reliable. The table below lists the alpha coefficients for the questionnaire questions.

Table 1. Cronbach's alpha test results of research variables

Factor	Number of Questions	Cronbach's alpha
Common values	6	891.0
Strategy	6	857.0
Organizational structure	9	813.0
Organizational systems	9	814.0
Management and leadership style	9	866.0
Employees	9	842.0
Manpower skills	9	831.0
Sales support	6	832.0
Monitoring and Feedback	3	815.0
Questionnaire	66	834.0

We analyzed the collected data in this study using the SPSS software package, and the results are presented in the form of descriptive findings, tables, graphs, and central statistics, and we also incorporated dispersion and inferential results in order to test for the hypotheses. Tests used in this study are the following: one-sample t-test for examining the effect or absence of each of the nine factors in the implementation of ERP in the organization; paired t-test for examining the existing and desired existence of each of the nine agents in the organization to identify gaps and shortcomings in the implementation of ERP in the organization. The Friedman test is intended to uncover the differences between nine factors and determine the priority between them for implementing ERP in an organization.

4. Findings

4.1. Statistics (Descriptive)

This section discusses the 9 factors that have been shown to be effective in implementing ERP in organizations. According to the table below, the average situation is only in 3 factors of common values, strategy and monitoring and feedback is above 3. The other 6 factors are lower than the value of 3 to indicate the unfavorable situation is the situation in the 6 factors. On the other hand, the optimal situation in all 9 factors is higher than 3, which shows the level of expectation of the respondents. In addition to the above results, comparing the current and favorable situation, it should be said that the gap between the two is in these factors, respectively: organizational systems, human resources skills, organizational structure, sales support, employees, management and leadership style, monitoring and feedback, common values, Strategy.

Table 2. Descriptive statistics

Variable	Status	Min	Max	Mode	Median	Average	Range	SD*
Common values	Available	83.2	17.4	17.3	41.3	45.3	33.1	33.0
	Desirable	67.3	50.4	17.4	08.4	04.4	83.0	21.0
Strategy	Available	40.2	4	40.2	3	06.3	60.1	53.0
	Desirable	4	60.4	4	20.4	17.4	60.0	20.0
Organizational structure	Available	67.1	69.3	89.1	16.2	40.2	2	62.0
	Desirable	33.3	56.4	11.4	11.4	10.4	22.1	26.0
Organizational systems	Available	1	5	11.1	33.1	73.1	4	07.1
	Desirable	4	5	5	5	79.4	1	33.0
Management and leadership style	Available	44.2	4	67.2	88.2	90.2	56.1	36.0
	Desirable	67.3	11.4	89.3	88.3	84.3	44.0	11.0
Employees	Available	94.1	72.3	50.2	50.2	57.2	78.1	41.0
	Desirable	28.3	17.4	72.3	77.3	82.3	89.0	21.0
Manpower skills	Available	56.1	44.3	67.1	77.1	01.2	89.1	53.0
	Desirable	33.3	4	33.3	66.3	62.3	67.0	19.0
Sales support	Available	33.2	4	67.2	83.2	95.2	67.1	44.0
	Desirable	50.3	4	50.3	66.3	70.3	50.0	17.0
Monitoring and Feedback	Available	67.2	4	63	3	27.3	33.1	42.0
	Desirable	4	33.4	4	4	13.4	02.0	16.0

Standard Deviation

Test results of research hypotheses

To test the above hypotheses, first a one-sample t-test was used for the optimal status of IRP implementation in companies and then a paired t-test was used to measure the comparison of the current and desired status.

Table 3. Hypotheses testing results

Factor	Aspects	Factor impact test results on ERP implementation				Comparison of available and desirable statuses			
		Real Average	Expected Average	Test value	Sig	Available average	Desirable average	Test value	Sig
Common values	General	04.4	3	98.36	0.00	45.3	04.4	-10.19	0.00
	The extent of the organization's belief in the benefits of ERP	95.3	3	75.19	0.00	22.4	95.3	46.8	0.00
	Organizational commitment to the project	14.4	3	21.53	0.00	67.2	14.4	-93.20	0.00
Strategy	General	17.4	3	62.43	0.00	06.3	17.4	-67.17	0.00
	Vision, mission and goals	53.4	3	55.38	0.00	96.3	53.4	-62.10	0.00
	IT Strategic Plan	62.3	3	10	0.00	71.1	62.3	-69.19	0.00
Organizational structure	General	10.4	3	35.32	0.00	40.2	10.4	-46.20	0.00
	Formalization	96.4	3	15.84	0.00	22.2	96.4	-23.36	0.00
	Organization size	80.3	3	38.7	0.00	28.2	80.3	-86.3	0.00
	IT role and position in the organization	51.3	3	25.14	0.00	96.2	51.3	-85.20	0.00
Organizational systems	General	79.4	3	02.41	0.00	73.1	79.4	-80.21	0.00
	IT infrastructure	86.4	3	17.42	0.00	70.1	86.4	-56.21	0.00
	Business processes	82.4	3	61.38	0.00	78.1	82.4	-44.21	0.00
	Available data and information	70.4	3	43.34	0.00	71.1	70.4	-63.21	0.00
Management and leadership style	General	84.3	3	56.56	0.00	90.2	84.3	-96.19	0.00
	Top management support	98.3	3	73.21	0.00	53.3	98.3	-63.11	0.00
	Organizational communications	22.4	3	44.30	0.00	88.1	22.4	-69.20	0.00
	Organizational culture	32.3	3	18.10	0.00	28.3	32.3	-72.1	09.0
Employees	General	82.3	3	40.29	0.00	57.2	82.3	-47.23	0.00
	HR management	46.3	3	9.9	0.00	55.2	46.3	-25.21	0.00
	Project team	05.4	3	15.32	0.00	80.2	05.4	-85.16	0.00
	Training	93.3	3	46.21	0.00	35.2	93.3	-22.11	0.00
Manpower skills	General	62.3	3	76.24	0.00	01.2	62.3	-01.20	0.00
	Top management skills	68.3	3	40.13	0.00	68.2	68.3	-97.14	0.00
	Employees skills	01.3	3	19.0	84.0	66.1	01.3	-09.14	0.00
	IT employees skills	19.4	3	35.37	0.00	68.1	19.4	-10.18	0.00
Sales support	General	70.3	3	80.31	0.00	95.2	70.3	-38.16	0.00
	Min customization	26.3	3	74.7	0.00	41.1	26.3	-53.23	0.00
	Systems vendor support and services	15.4	3	65.30	0.00	49.4	15.4	47.5	0.00
Monitoring & Feedback	General	13.4	3	30.53	0.00	13.4	13.4	-97.15	0.00

In general, the following spider diagram depicts the success factors of ERP implementation in organizations and companies in the three existing, desirable, and ideal situations.

Figure 1. Spider diagram of organizational evaluation for establishment of ERP in three statuses: available, desirable and ideal

Prioritize the status of the components affecting the implementation of ARP in the current and desired situation Friedman's analysis of variance was used to rank the components affecting the implementation of IRP in the current and desired situation. According to the result of the table below and referring to the value of the Chi-square test 333/92 with a significance level of 0.01, it can be said that there is a significant difference between the 9 factors of ERP implementation in the current situation and comparing the means, it should be said that the first priorities are Common values, monitoring and feedback, and strategy, respectively. In other words, the status of organizations in these three factors is most conducive to the implementation of IRP, and the last priorities are manpower skills, organizational systems, and organizational structure, which are more unfavorable than Saber. Implementation of ARP. The results of the Chi-square test 315/47 with a significance level of 0.01 showed that there is a significant difference between the 9 effective factors of implementing IRP in organizations and comparing the means, it should be said that important priorities for respondents to implement IRP in organizations are: : Organizational systems are organizational strategy and structure. Comparing this result with the priorities of the current situation, it can be said that the two factors of organizational systems and organizational structure, despite the high priority of the desired situation, have the lowest status in organizations.

Table 4. Results of 9 priority factors affecting ERP implementation

Factor	Available		Desirable	
	Value	Priority	Value	Priority
Common values	48.8	1	29.5	5
Strategy	36.6	3	65.6	2
Organizational structure	34.3	7	52.6	3
Organizational systems	13.2	8	60.8	1
Management and leadership style	63.5	5	66.3	6
Employees	72.3	6	50.3	7
Manpower skills	10.2	9	08.2	9
Sales support	6	4	47.2	8
Monitoring and Feedback	24.7	2	23.6	4
Test results	Chi-squared	92.335	Chi-squared	47.315
	Sig	01.0	Sig	01.0

Along with ranking the variables, the dimensions affecting the implementation of ARP in organizations are also ranked in the table below. Comparison between dimensions It should be said that the key priorities influencing the implementation of ARP in organizations are: the support and services of the system vendor, the extent of the organization's belief in the benefits of ERP, vision, mission, and goals, support of senior management, and organizational culture.

The results of the following table for the optimal position of the affective dimensions in the implementation of ERP in organizations indicate a significant difference based on 871.15 chi-square test with an error level of 0.01. Important priorities for influencing the implementation of IRP in organizations in the desired situation are formalization, IT infrastructure, business processes, available data and information, and vision, mission, and goals.

Table 5. The results of the test of prioritization of aspects affecting the implementation of ERP

Aspect	Available		Desirable	
	Value	Priority	Value	Priority
The extent of the organization's belief in the benefits of ERP	45.20	2	27.10	14
Organizational commitment to the project	91.12	7	63.12	9
Vision, mission and goals	64.19	3	93.16	5
IT Strategic Plan	90.5	20	99.6	16
Formalization	77.8	13	34.19	1
Organization size	03.9	12	37.10	12
IT role and position in the organization	52.12	9	33.5	18
IT infrastructure	98.5	19	47.18	2
Business processes	65.6	15	17.18	3
Available data and information	23.6	18	29.17	4
Top management support	82.17	4	36.10	13
Focus on Organizational communications	68.7	14	98.13	6
Organizational culture	65.16	5	88.3	19
HR management	43.11	10	64.5	17
Project team	08.14	6	43.11	10
Training	05.10	11	46.10	11
Top management skills	79.12	8	09.7	15
Employees skills	28.6	17	87.2	21
IT employees skills	57.6	16	40.13	7
Min customization	61.3	21	45.3	20
Systems vendor support and services	18.21	1	66.12	8
Test results	Chi-squared	85.876	Chi-squared	15.871
	Sig	01.0	Sig	01.0

5. Conclusions and suggestions

In the present study, considering the importance of reviewing and ranking the factors and obstacles affecting the implementation of ERP organizational resource planning systems in Iran and the existence of some challenges in this area, it was necessary to review and rank the factors affecting the success of ERP organizational resource planning to investigate the issue. It was discussed in the country. The research hypotheses and questions were examined in the form of several variables of shared values, strategies, structure, systems, leadership style, staff, skills, vendor support, monitoring and feedback, and ERP organizational resource planning system.

Based on nine hypotheses, this study investigated the relationship between nine factors and the ERP organizational resource planning system. Statistical tests and SPSS software were

used to test the data and hypotheses. As the results of the hypotheses are fully explained in the article and also summarized in the table, all nine hypotheses are accepted. The variables and hypotheses are later examined in existing as well as desired conditions. We have also ranked the variables in current and desired conditions. In each of the nine variables and hypotheses, there was a significant difference between the existing situation and the desired situation that the desired situation has a higher position and average than the current situation. In the current situation, the importance of the variables is in the order of structure, system, strategy, skills, common values, support, staff, monitoring and feedback, and leadership style, and in the desired situation, the importance of the variables is in the order of employees, skills, structure, common values, Monitoring and feedback, leadership style, strategy, support, and system.

The factor of shared values has a significant impact on the implementation of ERP in companies. If observed, this hypothesis was tested, which was accompanied by confirmation of the hypothesis. Which is consistent with the findings of Shiri et al. 2015 and Niknejad 1394. Common values include the beliefs, core ideas, significant meanings, or important beliefs that the organization instills in its members. These cases guide and guide the orientation of ERP organizational resource planning system towards performing tasks, goals, employees, community, etc.

A company's strategy plays a significant role in the implementation of ERP. This hypothesis was tested, consistent with the findings of Shiri et al. 2015 and Niknejad 1394, and Khanlari et al. 1393. According to the research results on significant advances in information technology, many organizations have moved to the use of integrated organizational information systems, leaving aside the islands and separate software systems. In such a situation, organizational resource planning systems have entered the field of management of organizations. They have integrated all organization processes by making fundamental changes in the information cycle and intra-organizational transactions. Successful operation of such a complex system, which affects an organization's entire business, requires compliance between this system and its organizer. If such a relationship does not exist, the probability of failure in this project will be very high. Organizations that use this system will usually have to make any changes to their organization processes and adapt to the logic and standard practices of the system. Otherwise, the probability of failure both in the system setup and its operation will be very high. The organizational resource planning system aligns its logic with the organizations and persuades them to move towards full integration and use standard and optimal processes, even if this integration is not helpful for them and the organization needs to use its business processes. Suppose the logic in this system is inconsistent with the current reason in an organization's business. In that case, the probability of failure of this system in the deployment phase or not achieving a competitive advantage over its use will be very high. The creators of enterprise resource planning systems state that they have incorporated the best methods for performing business processes in this system due to the extensive information they have gathered on performing work processes in different organizations in different industries and areas.

The structure factor has a significant impact on ERP implementation in companies. This hypothesis was tested, which is consistent with the findings of Shiri et al. 2015 and Niknejad

1394 and Shokri et al. 1390 and Khanlari and Kafei 1393. Organizational structure is the pattern of internal organizational relationships, authority, and the flow of communication within the organization. The organizational structure shows how employees report to the organization, several levels of organizational hierarchy, control area of managers and supervisors, working groups, and different organizational units and how the organization is formed with the help of these units and how to design the organization to ensure practical and effective interoperability. In the early years of its formation, the ERP organizational resource planning system was a tool used to assist in staffing and support activities, such as financial processes and human resources in organizations. Still, now it has played a much broader role in organizations than ever before. Strategies include customer relations, organizational performance management, supply chain management, organizational planning and analysis, and many other areas. Therefore, the success of the organizational resource planning system depends on the compatibility between this system and contingent organizational variables, such as organizational structure.

The operating system has a significant impact on ERP implementation in companies. As it was observed, this hypothesis was tested, which is somewhat consistent with the findings of Shiri et al., 2015; Ifindo and Nahr, 2007; Full Hoon, Delgado, 2006; Niknejad, 1394; and Yousefizadeh et al., 1397. The ERP enterprise resource planning system is, in fact, the culmination of the evolution of information systems in the present age. The capabilities of these systems have caused that in addition to the business sector, government, and non-profit organizations to use them and provide the basis for improving customer service. ERP enterprise resource planning system has played a vital role in changing the position and function of information technology in organizations. This system can be developed internally and externally. Still, due to the complexities in this area, many organizations have left the operation of these systems to vendors and manufacturers outside the organization. Suppliers of ERP enterprise resource planning systems offer their products in various modules. These modules can be used individually, or a combination of them can be provided to the organization to achieve organizational goals. Implementing ERP enterprise resource planning systems can cost organizations millions of dollars. The suppliers of these systems state that with the launch of these systems, the cost of information systems will be reduced, and the organization's operational efficiency will increase. Therefore, setting up an ERP enterprise resource planning system will be cost-effective.

The leadership style factor has a significant impact on ERP implementation in companies. This hypothesis was tested, which is consistent with the findings of Shiri et al. 2015 and Niknejad 1394 and Ebrahimi Kordler et al., 1390. Leadership can be defined as the ability to influence individuals to achieve goals. Establishing the organization's resource planning system is a significant organizational-cultural change rather than a change in the information system. This transformation must take place continuously and efficiently in the new organizational environment. One of the keys to establishing an organization's resource planning system is for management to be committed to the project, not just involved.

The employee factor has a significant impact on ERP implementation in companies. This hypothesis was tested, which is consistent with the findings of Shiri et al. 2015, Ifindo and Nahr 2007, Rezaei Manesh et al. 1396, Niknejad 1394, and Shokri et al. 1390. Successful

implementation of an ERP system requires the commitment and cooperation of all employees in all parts of the organization. Therefore, the role of employees in the success or failure of ERP implementation is inevitable. Employees must be convinced that the organization is committed to implementing ERP. They must recognize the need for change and be prepared appropriately for the transition to prevent resistance and disorder. The employees involved in the project are also crucial because they will be the system's users. In addition, they must have sufficient IT skills and knowledge to understand ERP.

The skills factor has a significant impact on the implementation of ERP in companies. As it was observed, this hypothesis was tested, which is consistent with the findings of Shiri et al. 2015, Ifindo and Nahr 2007, Full Hoon and Delgado 2006, Niknejad 1394, and Nazari and Survival 1389. A person or group of people with different abilities and skills should be responsible for the successful advancement of ERP projects. This group must first clearly define the scope of the project and its activities, including the number of systems used, the degree of participation of business units, and the amount of re-engineering required in the processes. The complexity of ERP implementation projects is very high in various aspects, including hardware, software, organizational issues, and the combination of these factors. In order to overcome these complexities, the project manager will use a wide range of skills and abilities, as well as specific planning and calculation. Because carrying out this project is associated with high risk, cost, and challenge, it is necessary to accurately manage all skills in all stages of its implementation. The duties of the executive team and project management include planning, organizing, scheduling project, monitoring and receiving feedback and risk management, preventing crises and large budget deviations, and planning and adjusting skills appropriate to the system.

The vendor support factor has a significant impact on the implementation of ERP in companies. As observed, this hypothesis was tested, which is consistent with the findings of him et al. In 2005, Rezaei Manesh et al. 1396, and the improvement of Asl et al., 2012. The organization must select the appropriate vendors that are able to provide a flexible ERP system. When choosing a new ERP system, several criteria should be considered, some of which are: system flexibility, user-friendliness and ease of implementation, usability, integration, compatibility, and upgrade. The salesperson should provide the training as well as after-sales support; because ERP has more or less complex applications for self-learning. It should also be considered that each department within the organization uses part of its own software. Therefore, some kind of specialized training is required for each unit. Market share, reputation, number of consultants, number of installations performed, support infrastructure, and past implementations are important factors that show the seller's commitment to production. Also, due to the high cost of installation and the costs incurred during implementation and use, service and support are vital factors in ERP implementation. Iranian managers must carefully select the right vendor to provide proper support and maintenance of the system. Vendor support in the form of continuous technical assistance, maintenance, updating, and user-specific training; an important factor in the success of ERP implementation in the next steps.

Feedback and monitoring have a significant impact on the implementation of ERP in companies. If it was observed, this hypothesis was tested, which was confirmed and is

consistent with the findings of Alizadeh et al., 2005. Measuring and evaluating the performance of an organization's resource planning project is a critical factor in ensuring the success of system implementation. To evaluate the effect of the new system on the business of the organization, performance measurement criteria are precisely defined and determined. These metrics indicate how the system is performing and may include timely outputs, net profit margin, ordering time to customer delivery, inventory turnover, vendor performance, and more. In the implementation of organizational resource planning systems, in addition to technical performance such as system reliability, other aspects such as flexibility, speed, timelines, costs, etc. Are also considered. Many researchers suggest a balanced scorecard evaluation method that includes four dimensions: finance, customer, in-house business, and learning and creativity.

One of the valuable benefits of ERP systems is the creation of shared value across corporate business activities. However, it is suggested by this article that purchasing this system will not only provide these benefits to the organization but also provide the conditions and key factors for ERP success. An important factor for the successful implementation of an ERP system is monitoring and feedback.

It is recommended that the project management and top management of the organization be informed of the performance and direct impact of ERP on the business with monthly or weekly reports. It is recommended that participatory programs be used to increase employee participation in the ERP system. In choosing the system, organizations should pay attention to the operational capacity of the system, the reliability of the system, adaptation to existing systems, the ability to upgrade the system, low ownership costs, and the use of the latest technology in the system. In the working group to plan the establishment of an ERP system, people with many skills and technical abilities should be used. Facilitate information design among the members of the design team and also in interaction with the whole organization and inform the results and objectives of each stage of the ERP system to all employees of the organization. To be created. Skills are an important factor in ERP implementation it is recommended to use the technical skills of specialists and consultants inside and outside the organization to establish an ERP system. Deployment of ERP systems is very important for upgrading open structures. These systems can assist organizational structures by creating integration and coordination, and enable access to organizational data and information.

ERP system by creating a systemic attitude and by creating compatibility in organizational information will lead to the organization's coordination with changes and external conditions and will also increase the work efficiency of employees and strengthen the correct performance of work and reduce rework, so it is suggested that organizations pay attention. To do it multiply. In order to better implement the ERP system, it is suggested that the leaders of the organization, using supportive leadership styles, express their support and encouragement of this model and emphasize the need to implement it in the organization. There should also be coordination and cooperation between different parts of the organization. Before deciding to implement the organization's resource planning system, managers should pay close attention to the skills and abilities of their organization to accept this system. According to the results, it is suggested that the study and modeling of strategic

and quantitative goals of the business and its existing structure align the goals of the processes with the ERP system in the best possible way.

Due to the fact that in this research, system, and structure were recognized as important factors in implementing ERP. Therefore, according to the facilities of the organization in order to increase the productivity of the organizational structure and the results of the research, the most important factors Important to the organization include the existence of hardware and software infrastructure in the field of information technology, computer culture, organizational size, and process reengineering in the industries under study. Therefore, it is suggested that managers and leaders consider the above-mentioned issues in choosing the desired system. It is suggested that monitoring and feedback, review, identification, and design of processes in different areas of work be done through a standard method and identification of process elements of each process. Organizations need to select the right vendor to support and maintain the system properly.

Vendor support in the form of continuous technical support, maintenance, and updating is an important factor in the successful implementation of ERP. According to the results of the research, it is suggested that the leadership of the organization announce its practical commitment to the implementation of the system, with the participation of employees and the allocation of valuable resources to it, until the end of its implementation. There are other models to assess the organizational readiness to implement the ERP system. Other researchers are suggested to use other models such as the combat model, Raymonds model, De Switzerland model, Nayakara, etc. In future research, critical factors in ERP implementation can be classified according to the nature and effectiveness of the ERP system and their effectiveness can be determined in terms of an internal or external organization. One of the limitations of the research was that some people avoided answering the questionnaire and this caused the collection of the questionnaire to be delayed. Because variables such as gender, age, education, and work experience were mentioned in the questionnaire, in some cases none of these variables were answered.

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